

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВО ПРИОБРЕТЕННОГО ЗНАНИЯ ОБУЧАЕМЫХ С ПОМОЩЬЮ КОЭФФИЦИЕНТА ВОСПРИЯТИЯ

Халдаров Х.А.

к.т.н., доцент

Khaldarov1946@mail.ru

Муҳамеджанова Гўзал Жавлон қизи

Ташкентский педагогический университет

Ташпулатов Равшанбек Хуснутдинович

Ташкентский технический университет им. И. Каримова

Аннотация: данная исследовательская работа посвящена расчёта качество приобретенного знания обучаемых, с использованием коэффициента восприятия, с помощью эргономической модели процесса обучения.

Ключевые слова и направления: эргономика, моделирование, математика, методы, процесс обучения, знание, качество, образовательные системы, теория матриц, коэффициент восприятия.

DETERMINING THE QUALITY OF STUDENTS' ACQUIRED KNOWLEDGE USING THE PERCEPTION COEFFICIENT

Khaldarov Kh.A.

Ph.D., Associate Professor

Khaldarov1946@mail.ru

Muhamedzhanova Guzal Javlon qizi

Tashkent Pedagogical University

Tashpulatov Ravshanbek Khusnutdinovich

Tashkent Technical University named after I.Karimov

Abstract: This research paper is devoted to calculating the quality of students' acquired knowledge using the perception coefficient, using an ergonomic model of the learning process.

Keywords and areas: ergonomics, modeling, mathematics, methods, learning process, knowledge, quality, educational systems, matrix theory, perception coefficient.

INTRODUCTIONS. Innovation in education is in high demand, which requires even more necessary and essential development of personnel in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, in order to train personnel to the required level, it is necessary to create an educational environment that meets aesthetic, ethical, and ergonomic requirements from the outset. This environment supports the development of specialists using information and communication technologies, mathematical, simulation, and ergonomic modeling methods to improve the quality of the learning process and knowledge acquisition [1-13].

The purpose of this research is to develop and create a mathematical (or other types of) model of the learning process in knowledge acquisition based on an ergonomic model, taking into account the perception coefficient. That is, at what distance or position can a teacher impart maximum knowledge to students, or can students acquire knowledge sufficiently and effectively? This also applies to the use of various learning tools – (LT), intelligent systems (IS), and others, regardless of the type of learning.

By definition: Ergonomics is a science that is developed and created to study various fields of science, technology, and education. It is used in: technical developments/solutions, sports, mechanical engineering, medicine, pedagogy, etc. Ergonomics as a science of research and teaching.

Analysis and synthesis of the teaching process with an ergonomic perspective.

Establishing logical and informational relationships between pedagogical ergonomics and the learning process in higher education institutions.

A systematic approach to researching problems in the field of teaching ergonomics.

Selecting methods for calculating econometric models of teaching ergonomics.

Analysis of the obtained research results and proposals.

Since the learning process takes place in classrooms, regardless of the type of instruction-lecture, practical, laboratory, or independent-they are all arranged differently in classrooms, i.e., in a radial, circular, or radial-circular arrangement.

METHODS. The goal is to construct an ergonomic model of the learning process based on the arrangement and distance between the instructor and students in the classroom, where the quality of acquired knowledge can be measured and calculated. To achieve this, it is necessary to conduct a study using an ergonomic model of the learning process, taking into account various parameters, indicators, and factors in the acquisition of knowledge. Our task is to explore the unknown, but one

in which we are always directly involved – in this learning process using ergonomic modeling.

Ergonomic indicators in teaching are an essential argument in conducting research and calculating the quality of learning. This includes taking into account and determining:

- the distance between the student and the teacher in the classroom [14, 17];
- the informational relationship between the student and the teacher [8];
- the logical relationship between the student and the teacher [8];
- the location of the student and the electronic whiteboard in the classroom;
- the location of the student and the learning environment in the classroom [17];
- the location of the student and intelligent systems in the classroom [19, 20];
- and the student's perception coefficient during the lesson (lecture, practical, and laboratory). For example, a radial arrangement [5] is proposed for existing classrooms in universities, taking into account the interaction between the instructor and students (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Radial arrangement of students in the classroom.

Currently, from the above arrangements between the student and the instructor, for determining.

Table 1.

Acquired knowledge	I've mastered it	I can imagin	I haven't mastered i	I haven't mastered it
1.0	0.75	0.5	0.25	0
5	4	3	2	1

Then, by conducting a survey of students, we will obtain Table 2, and the result of assessing the quality of acquired knowledge using the perception coefficient will be presented as in Figure 1.

Table 2.

Чарли Ч	3	4	5	4	4	3	4	5	4	5	4	4
Набока К	4	4	4	5	5	4	3	4	5	3	4	5
Алмаев Р	3	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	4
Алиев К	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	5
Карпов В	3	3	3	4	3	4	3		4	3	4	3
Пан Чори	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	4
Янг Г	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	4
Штейн С	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	4	4
Хан И	3	4	5	3	4	5	3	4	5	3	4	5
Трамп Д	5	4	3	3	4	5	5	4	3	3	4	5
Левин Д	3	3	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	4
Вакил Д	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

Figure 1.

To measure the learner's perception coefficient, the inverse of Table 1 is performed, taking into account the learner survey.

This research project is a beginning, i.e., an experimental one, in determining the quality of acquired knowledge using the perception coefficient.

CONCLUSION. To obtain a complete research result, the following additional steps are necessary:

- construct a mathematical model for assessing acquired knowledge during the learning process.
- use various mathematical methods to solve the problem.
- this development is essential for determining the quality of educational systems not only for one group, but for all higher education institutions as a whole, which is relevant today.
- when designing the learning process, it is necessary to determine logical and informational relationships.

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